

From Circuit to Market: Assessing the Sustainability of Formula E and Its Impact in Brazil

*Del circuito al mercado: Evaluando la sostenibilidad de la
Fórmula E y su impacto en Brasil*
*Do Circuito ao Mercado: Avaliação da Sustentabilidade da
Fórmula E e Seu Impacto no Brasil*

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Celso Jacobavicius¹

celso.jacobavicius@fatec.sp.gov.br

Claudia Vieira Daroncho²

claudiavs@gmail.com

Celio Daroncho¹

celio.daroncho@fatec.sp.gov.br

1 – Faculdade de Tecnologia do Estado de São Paulo – Fatec Zona Leste
2 – Unidade de Pós-graduação do Centro Paula Souza – UPEP CPS

Resumo:

A demanda por mobilidade urbana continua a aumentar e a paisagem em transformação tem profundas repercussões em uma variada gama de questões, como saúde, segurança, água, transporte e consumo de energia. Por esta razão, para alcançar a urbanização sustentável, as cidades devem gerar melhores oportunidades de emprego, expandir a infraestrutura necessária, garantir acesso igualitário aos serviços, preservar os recursos naturais dentro da cidade e áreas circunvizinhas. Neste contexto, mesmo no automobilismo (particularmente na FIA), as tendências futuras começam a se orientar para questões de sustentabilidade e há um crescente interesse em avaliar o perfil de sustentabilidade dos veículos de corrida. A proteção ambiental e a eco mobilidade representam o principal desafio enfrentado pela Fórmula E, oferecendo veículos elétricos (VEs) projetados para combinar tecnologia, inovação e sustentabilidade, bem como permitir a transição para cidades inteligentes de baixo carbono num futuro próximo. Até hoje, as questões de sustentabilidade na Fórmula E foram tratadas exclusivamente em nível de sistema (ou seja, logística e gestão, viagens, infraestrutura e assim por diante), mas não existem estudos em nível de componentes. O desenvolvimento tecnológico relacionado ao campo de desempenho em corridas também tem potencial para impulsionar a inovação, apoiando assim a melhoria contínua do *powertrain* elétrico em termos de eficiência, desempenho e uso otimizado de materiais, como terras raras para motores elétricos e materiais ativos para baterias. O objetivo do artigo é o desenvolvimento e implementação de uma abordagem metodológica personalizada para avaliar os impactos ambientais de todo o Ciclo de Vida (CV) de um motor elétrico da Fórmula E. A coleta de dados primários é funcional para aumentar o conhecimento e o inventário relacionados à aplicação específica. Ao mesmo tempo, os resultados fornecem indicações úteis para melhorar o desenvolvimento do produto sob a perspectiva do ecodesign e

garantir a transferência de tecnologia dos carros de corrida de alto desempenho para os veículos comerciais.

Palavras-chave: Fórmula E; automobilismo; motores elétricos; inovação; sustentabilidade; popularidade.

Abstract:

The demand for urban mobility continues to increase, and the changing landscape has profound repercussions on many issues, such as health, safety, water, transport and energy consumption. For this reason, to achieve sustainable urbanization, cities must generate better employment opportunities, expand the necessary infrastructure, ensure equal access to services, and preserve natural resources within the city and surrounding areas. In this context, even in motorsport (particularly in the FIA), future trends are beginning to orient towards sustainability issues, and there is a growing interest in assessing the sustainability profile of racing vehicles. Environmental protection and eco-mobility represent the main challenges facing Formula E, offering electric vehicles (EVs) designed to combine technology, innovation, and sustainability and enable the *transition to low-carbon intelligent cities shortly. To date, sustainability issues in Formula E have been addressed exclusively at the system level (i.e., logistics and management, travel, infrastructure and so on), but no component-level studies exist. Technological development related to racing performance also has the potential to drive innovation, thereby supporting the continuous improvement of the electric powertrain in terms of efficiency, performance, and optimized use of materials such as rare earths for electric motors and active materials for batteries. The paper aims to develop and implement a customized methodological approach to assess the environmental impacts of a Formula E electric engine's Life Cycle (CV). At the same time, the results provide valuable indications for improving product development from the perspective of ecodesign and ensuring the transfer of technology from high-performance racing cars to commercial vehicles.*

Keywords: Formula E; motorsport; electric motors; innovation; sustainability; popularity.

Resumen:

La demanda de movilidad urbana sigue aumentando y el panorama cambiante tiene profundas repercusiones en una amplia gama de cuestiones, como la salud, la seguridad, el agua, el transporte y el consumo de energía. Por esta razón, para lograr una urbanización sostenible, las ciudades deben generar mejores oportunidades de empleo, ampliar la infraestructura necesaria, garantizar el acceso igualitario a los servicios, preservar los recursos naturales dentro de la ciudad y las áreas circundantes. En este contexto, incluso en el automovilismo (particularmente en la FIA), las tendencias futuras están comenzando a orientarse hacia cuestiones de sostenibilidad y existe un creciente interés en evaluar el perfil de sostenibilidad de los vehículos de carreras. La protección del medio ambiente y la ecomovilidad representan el principal reto al que se enfrenta la Fórmula E, que ofrece vehículos eléctricos (VE) diseñados para combinar tecnología, innovación y sostenibilidad, así como para permitir la transición hacia ciudades inteligentes bajas en carbono en un futuro próximo. Hasta la fecha, los problemas de sostenibilidad en la Fórmula E se han tratado exclusivamente a nivel de sistema (es decir, logística y gestión, viajes, infraestructura, etc.), pero no hay estudios a nivel de componentes. El desarrollo tecnológico relacionado con el campo del rendimiento en las carreras también tiene el potencial de impulsar la innovación, apoyando así la mejora continua del tren motriz eléctrico en términos de eficiencia, rendimiento y uso optimizado de materiales como las tierras raras para los motores eléctricos y los materiales activos para las baterías. El objetivo del artículo es el desarrollo e implementación de un enfoque metodológico

personalizado para evaluar los impactos ambientales de todo el Ciclo de Vida (CV) de un motor eléctrico de Fórmula E. Al mismo tiempo, los resultados proporcionan indicaciones útiles para mejorar el desarrollo de productos desde la perspectiva del ecodiseño y garantizar la transferencia de tecnología de los coches de carreras de alto rendimiento a los vehículos comerciales.

Palabras clave: Fórmula E; automovilismo; motores eléctricos; innovación; sostenibilidad; popularidad.

1. INTRODUCTION

Formula E has become an innovative and disruptive force in the motorsport industry, promoting sustainability and electric vehicle technology. This phenomenon attracts motorsport enthusiasts and car manufacturers, offering a combination of sporting competition, technological innovation and environmental awareness. Although it has gained global popularity, especially regarding its positive environmental impact compared to Formula 1, Formula E still faces challenges regarding recognition and acceptance, especially in Brazil. Historically, innovation in motorsport has always been met with resistance. Still, since its inception in 2014, Formula E has gradually gained relevance, mainly due to its all-electric cars offering a sustainable solution to motorsport. However, the competition still faces obstacles, such as technological limitations and cultural prejudices.

The environmental impact of combustion-powered cars is significant, contributing to global warming and public health problems. Formula E promotes a more sustainable alternative, with electric vehicles that regenerate energy and use recyclable materials, in line with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The automotive market is adapting, with many manufacturers partnering with Formula E, as it acts as a laboratory for innovations that will eventually be applied to commercial production cars.

Formula E's popularity in Brazil has grown, driven by television broadcasts, local partnerships and the promotion of sustainability by influencers and celebrities. However, competition with traditional sports such as Formula 1 and the need to educate the public about electric vehicle benefits remain challenging. Integrating sports journalism with Formula E is essential to increase its visibility and relevance. Studies show that the structure of emissions can influence public perception, highlighting sustainability and technological innovation.

Despite the financial difficulties faced during the pandemic, Formula E continues to grow in audience and impact, attracting an increasingly diverse and diverse audience. To cement its position, Formula E must continue to promote sustainability in its broadcasts and events, educating and engaging audiences on the benefits of electric vehicles and environmentally friendly practices.

According to [1], Formula E has become a phenomenon in the contemporary motorsport industry, proving to be a disruptive competition that challenges the established conventions of the traditional motorsport industry. Its innovative

approach to motorsport and electric vehicle technology has generated growing interest among enthusiasts and industry participants. Formula E plays a vital role in this historic moment, offering an option to combine sporting competitiveness with technological innovation and environmental sustainability.

The automotive industry faces several challenges in the 21st century, from changing consumer preferences for sustainable mobility to growing environmental awareness. As electric cars become more popular and several car manufacturers become investors, the design, production and perception of racing vehicles are changing. However, the visibility and popularity of Formula E are still not as expected, especially in Brazil.

This study aims to develop and implement a customized methodological approach to assess the environmental impacts throughout the entire Life Cycle (HP) of an electric motor used in Formula E. This study aims to collect primary data to enrich the ecological inventory and increase specific knowledge about the application of electric motors in racing vehicles. Furthermore, the results aim to provide guidelines to improve the development of products based on eco-design and facilitate the transfer of high-performance technologies from racing cars to commercial vehicles.

The study is justified by evident concern regarding using natural resources, the scarcity of non-renewable resources, and the high costs of obtaining and producing these inputs. It is also based on its increasing popularity due to its ecological appeal.

2. DEVELOPMENT

In recent years, the growing popularity of Formula E as an innovative and sustainable series in the world of motorsport has sparked great interest among racing enthusiasts and environmental advocates; important facts to highlight its importance not only as a high-performance sport but also as a way to drive the adoption of clean technologies and raise awareness of pressing environmental issues [1].

However, as shown in Figure 1, Formula E is still not as well-known as Formula 1 [2]. Comparing the economic data from 2023, when these competitions were held in the city of São Paulo, it is clear that Formula E has not yet gained the space it deserves.

Figure 1 Comparison of Audience and Economic Impacts between Formula 1 and Formula E in 2023, in São Paulo [2]

2.1 Innovation and Formula E

Innovation can be considered very broad, but [3] brings an exciting concept: innovation is a new commodity; that is, it can be a new production method or better-quality products, and all innovation must be introduced to the market. Based on this concept of innovation and its evolution, it is possible to identify how this process affects sports in terms of social, economic, technological, and organizational aspects. In this context, Formula E emerged in 2014 and has gradually stood out, mainly in innovation. [4] presents a study that shows that Formula E is Formula 1 with 100% electric vehicles and provides an essential parameter of influence on sustainability's social and sporting importance.

According to [1], the attempt to bring electrification to motorsports is not recent. Camille Jenatzy pioneered these attempts in 1898. In 1913, Henry Ford and Thomas Edison made a new attempt to develop an electric racing car. However, the project failed due to a lack of technological support and commercial conflicts. From then on, oil began to influence companies increasingly and transform society's lives, reducing the already limited space for the notoriety of electric car technology [1].

In 1950, with the creation of the first Formula 1 world championship, car manufacturers were already involved in producing gasoline-powered vehicles, making the competition an essential means of commercially and culturally promoting this propulsion model [5]. Formula E emerged in 2014 as a significant disruption within global motorsports. That year, the competition generated many vital comments and messages about sustainability, entrepreneurship, and business skills. In addition, the controversy surrounding the case of pollutant emissions by the Volkswagen company in 2015 helped create a perfect scenario for the consolidation of the sport [6].

Over the years, mistakes have also been made that have compromised Formula E regarding the energy capacity of the cars' batteries. In the first editions, 2014-2018, drivers had to make a pit stop and change cars, as the batteries were insufficient for the entire route. Another problem is that the cars do not have as

much noise as Formula 1 cars, which sometimes leads to disappointment among the captive motorsport audience [7]. [8] He makes several considerations about electric vehicles and says, "Electric cars are simply the last great myth before the ecological disaster hits everyone."

2.2 Sustainability

CO2 emissions are intensified by the use of combustion engines that are directly linked to global warming, which increases the speed and occurrence of melting, sea level rise, desertification, changes in precipitation and flooding, in addition to directly impacting human health, causing respiratory problems, heart disease and other health problems [1]. From the combustion of fossil fuels, the key to leading a natural transition to low-carbon intelligent cities is to find the right balance between technology, innovation and sustainability [4, 9].

In this context, Formula 1 has a significant adverse environmental impact, particularly concerning CO2 emissions, since during a race, each Formula 1 car emits approximately 0.5 kg of CO2 per kilometer traveled, considering that a typical Formula 1 race covers approximately 305 km, there is an emission per car of roughly 152.5 kilograms of CO2 [1, 3]. With 20 cars competing in a race, total emissions can reach approximately 3,050 kg of CO2 during the race, or approximately 70,150 kilograms of CO2 emitted in races alone throughout the season. This does not include test broadcasts, equipment transportation, team travel, infrastructure and people's access to each event [1, 4].

Analyzing the global context, Formula E stands out as a pioneering and exclusive category in motorsport in promoting sustainability with electric engines and innovative measures with renewable energies and efficient logistics with the use of recyclable materials since its creation in 2014, directly contributing to 10 of the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in addition to participating in the UN's "Climate Neutral Now" initiative to reduce harmful gases and achieve climate neutrality by 2050, by the Paris Treaty [1, 4]. In Brazil, the modality has ISO 20121 certifications for sustainable events [10] and ISO 14001 for its environmental management system [11]. Despite this, there is still pollution in the extraction and handling of materials from electric car batteries, contributing to CO2 emissions.

The category currently has the Gen3 car version, with a maximum power of 350 kW and energy regeneration of 600 kW. This means that the car recovers much of the energy demanded during braking. The engines convert more than 95% of electrical energy into mechanical energy. In contrast, in Formula 1, the engines convert around 40%, producing 40% of the energy consumed in the race through regenerative braking [1, 4, 9].

Table 1 compares some aspects of Formula 1's performance and characteristics with Formula E's [12], and many items bring the two categories closer together.

Table 01 Comparison between Formula E and Formula 1 cars [12]

Feature	Formula E	Formula 1
Maximum speed	320 km/h	340 km/h
Energy recovery	Up to 0.5 MJ per lap	2 MJ per lap
Length	5,016.2 mm	5,000 mm
Height	1,023.4 mm	950 mm
Wide	1,700 mm	2,000 mm
Battle	2,970.5 mm	3,050 - 3,150 mm
Weight (without pilot)	760 kg	798 kg

The goal of sustainable racing has attracted many car manufacturers and technology companies, including Citroën, Renault, Mahindra, Audi, BMW, Mercedes-Benz and Faraday Future. Many sponsors and teams have flocked to Formula E, emphasizing commercial, political and social issues. Formula E is seen as the future of the common market for motorsport and is essential for the transition and popularization of electric cars [9, 13].

Formula E is a disruptive category in motorsport, redefining the boundaries of what a sport can be through a unique fusion of entertainment, sustainability, technology and innovation. It addresses climate change, offers electric vehicles as a solution to air pollution in urban centers and breaks down barriers to the electric vehicle market. It acts as a laboratory for the development of the automotive industry, making electric vehicles more accessible and efficient [6].

2.3 Popularity and Media

Formula E, an all-electric racing series with a format similar to Formula 1, stands out for its green credentials and efforts to position itself as a sustainable alternative in the global motorsport scene. However, one question remains: will Formula E be able to attract a significant audience in Brazil, a country passionate about motorsport? Since its inception, Formula E has been gaining popularity in Brazil, with the introduction of a race in São Paulo in the 2022-2023 season being an important milestone in increasing the visibility and interest of the Brazilian public [2]. The popularity of Formula E in Brazil can be attributed to several promotion and engagement strategies, including live broadcasts on television and streaming platforms.

Despite its growth, Formula E faces challenges to establish itself in Brazil. Among the main obstacles is competition with other motorsports, such as Formula 1 and Stock Car, which already have an established fan base. In addition, the need to educate the public about the advantages of electric vehicles and sustainability remains a barrier. On the other hand, Formula E has numerous opportunities to expand its popularity in Brazil, as education and awareness, investing in educational programs that inform about the benefits of electric vehicles and the importance of sustainability, can help build a more informed and engaged fan base. Expansion to other cities, such as holding races in major Brazilian cities besides São Paulo, can increase visibility and interest in the series. With their environmental concerns, cities like Rio de Janeiro and Belo Horizonte can be strategic destinations. Technological Innovations and Interactive Experiences By

integrating technological innovations into broadcasts and offering interactive experiences to viewers, such as augmented reality and virtual events, it can attract a younger and more technologically engaged audience.

Recently, sports journalism has evolved into a hybrid model that combines traditional reporting styles with social media, allowing more opportunities for journalists to create stories using different frameworks. As information about athletes, teams, and the sport becomes more readily available, an increasingly dominant overlap of sports coverage becomes increasingly dominant. Entertainment and celebrities.

Despite this shift to a hybrid model, and although media producers often do not intentionally choose specific frames over others, they are still limited by time and/or content constraints. They can only select a limited number of relevant stories. [7] analyzed the portrayal of Formula E's Environmental Sustainability efforts in British and Flemish newspapers and revealed that Environmental Sustainability was not a dominant frame but appeared as part of other Formula E frames.

A preliminary analysis of the live broadcasts gave a clear picture of their recurring structure. Each consisted of three macro sections often associated with live motorsport broadcasting: a pre-race section, a race section and a post-race section. Each macro section constituted a subunit of analysis for identifying frames, allowing a more detailed comparison of the broadcasts [7].

Regarding the structuring of Formula E broadcasts, [7] presents that the analysis revealed eight different structures used in the broadcasts, which varied in dominance in different broadcast sections. For example, the "Strong Eco-Message" structure was notable in the pre-race section of the 2014 broadcast. However, it was less prominent in subsequent broadcasts, indicating a potential novelty effect rather than sustained importance. Similarly, [7] addresses dominant structures, such as traditional motorsport structures, where conventional motorsport structures present challenges and uncertainties, highlighting the difficulties and uncertainties associated with Formula E attracting fans from traditional motorsport. Proper motorsport, ensuring the legitimacy of the sport and its entertainment value, essential to retaining traditional audiences and managing conflicts, emphasizing the drama and danger inherent in motorsport and, finally, non-traditional structures as novelties, presenting Formula E as innovative and technologically advanced, creating engagement with the audience, through fan involvement through interactive features, facilitated mainly by social media.

Regarding Formula E's financial performance and growth, despite the economic impact of the coronavirus pandemic, Formula E has resumed investment in its future. The 2022 financial report indicated record revenues of €181 million, although losses also increased to €15.2 million. The series hosted more races than ever, contributing to increased sponsorship and race licensing revenue.

Regarding the expansion of Formula E's audience, as seen in Table 02, and can be accessed at [13] for more details on the development of the television audience for Formula E races, it grew by 20% in 2022, reaching 381 million viewers

worldwide. Social media followers also increased by 15%, with a significant increase in online video views, reflecting the series' growing popularity and digital presence. This data may raise the idea that this popularity may be reflected in the sports market and increase its penetration.

Table 02 *Formula E wins, losses and popularity [13]*

Year	Revenue (million euros)	Loss (million euros)	Online hearing	TV audience (millions)
2013	0.00	0.23	n/a	n/a
2014	1.43	6.78	n/a	n/a
2015	20.99	62.18	n/a	n/a
2016	56.60	35.29	270,000	192
2017	94.47	20.79	220,000	223
2018	133.44	26.41	368,000	330
2019	161.53	10.56	400,000	411
2020	142.84	0.06	n/a	239 (unofficial)
2021	168.72	12.58	n/a	316
2022	181.45	65.00	n/a	381

Integrating a dedicated sustainability segment into each broadcast system may be beneficial to "naturalize" Environmental Sustainability into Formula E's broadcast systems. This approach would align with sustainability's growing social importance and attract a younger, more environmentally conscious audience. [5] They discuss in their paper how to build a passionate and engaged fan base locally and globally, not only during race days but also among themselves, under great uncertainty; the characteristics of service innovation (disruptive/digital); and the varied possibilities and value of intertwining the physical and virtual worlds.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The research used a bespoke methodological approach to assessing the environmental impacts of a Formula E electric powertrain's life cycle (LC). The analysis showed that while Formula E represents a significant step forward in sustainable innovation in motorsport, there are opportunities to improve powertrain development and technology transfer to the commercial vehicle market.

The results show that Formula E, with its state-of-the-art electric motors, has a reduced environmental impact compared to internal combustion vehicles. However, there are still areas for improvement, such as production efficiency and management of used batteries. The methodology provides a valuable model for assessing and minimizing environmental impacts, which can be adapted and applied to other areas of the automotive industry.

To optimize Formula E's contribution to sustainability and ensure effective technology transfer, the series must continue to invest in eco-design practices and continuous improvements in engine efficiency. Integrating sustainability

policies and sound environmental regulation will also play a key role.

The research suggests that Formula E should adopt a more systematic approach to communicating its environmental developments, emphasizing technology transfer and the positive impact that electric powertrains can have on the commercial vehicle market. In addition, it recommends implementing public policies and regulatory frameworks that encourage sustainable innovation and promote the integration of clean technologies in the automotive sector.

This alignment between the evaluation methodology and the results obtained reinforces Formula E's role as a catalyst for sustainable change in motorsport. It offers a clear path to maximizing this innovation's environmental and technological benefits.

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